

To Study the Sex Ratio of Similar Size City and Nanded City

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1. Introduction

One of the important indicators of social development in the high level of literacy and educational attainment is considered to be an important factor in the process of modernization. Nanded city literacy structure was studied in the period of 1991 to 2011.

A high level of literacy reflects the dynamic character of a city population. The Table indicates the literacy structure of the Nanded city during the period of 1971-2011. In 1971, 1981, 1991, 2001 and 2011 census, it was of 43.6, 53.88, 59.14, 68.87 and 74.8 percent respectively; it was accordingly increased decade by decade. Male literacy rate was observed higher in 1971 and 1981 census, it was 67.45 and 63.42 percent. After the 1991 census, male literacy rate was decreased but female literacy rate was increased. In the 2011 census, 54.47 males and 45.53 percent females are literate in Nanded city. Its main cause is development of educational facilities in the city as well as in the state.

2. Study Area of Similar Size Cities

Here an attempt to select similar cities on the basis of population. The population of selected

cities is as per 2011 Census and the population is near to $\pm 1,00,000$.

Geographical Location of Similar Size Cities

Sr. No.	Name of the City	Latitude	Longitude	Figure Number
1	Amravati	20 ⁰ 50'17" N. to 20 ⁰ 59'16" N.	77 ⁰ 42'08" E to 77 ⁰ 49'47" E	5.1
2	Akola	20 ⁰ 41'34" N. to 20 ⁰ 43'41" N.	76 ⁰ 58'54" E. to 77 ⁰ 00'40" E	5.2
3	Jalgaon	20 ⁰ 56'18" N. to 21 ⁰ 02'47" N.	75 ⁰ 30'45" E. to 75 ⁰ 36'36" E	5.3
4	Kolhapur	16 ⁰ 39'09" N. to 16 ⁰ 46'03" N.	74 ⁰ 11'18" E. to 74 ⁰ 16'49" E	5.4
5	Malegaon	20 ⁰ 31'43" N. to 20 ⁰ 34'08" N.	74 ⁰ 31'19" E. to 74 ⁰ 32'55" E.	5.5
6	Sangli	16 ⁰ 46'21" N. to 16 ⁰ 53'36" N.	74 ⁰ 31'38" E. to 74 ⁰ 41'19" E.	5.6

3. Objective:

1. To Study The Sex Ratio Of Similar Size City And Nanded City

4. Data Base & Methodology:

The required data present study has collected from primary and Secondary Data Collection by various government departments, i.g. District Census Hand Book of Nanded District 1981,1991 ,2001 and 2011, Socio-Economic Review and District Statistical Abstract of Nanded District 1981,1991 ,2001 and 2011, District Gazetteer of Nanded District, Various branch offices of Nanded Zilla Parishad. Various Municipal Corporation Offices of the Nanded District, Industrial Development Corporation (MIDC), Town planning Department Nanded, Nanded Municipal Reports.

Data collected data has tabulated, classified, presented, compared and interpreted with help of various appropriate statistical methods. Tables, Diagrams and maps have used at appropriate place and their interpretation has realized the present study

5. Result & Discussion:

Sex Ratio

Following Table shows the similar size cities' sex ratio in 2001. The sex ratio of Amravati, Nanded, Kolhapur, Sangli, Jalgaon, Akola and Malegaon city was 989, 916, 914, 947, 905, 938 and 960 females per thousand male respectively. The sex ratio of Amravati city was higher than the other cities and Jalgaon city had lowest sex ratio than the other cities.

**Similar Size Cities'
Sex Ratio- 2001**

Name of City	Male	Female	Sex Ratio
Amravati	268247	265263	989
Nanded	224813	205920	916
Kolhapur	255778	233789	914
Sagali	224300	212481	947
Jalgaon	193496	175122	905
Akola	206649	193871	938
Malegaon	208868	200539	960

Source: Census 2001.

Table shows the similar size cities' sex ratio during the period of 2011 census. The sex ratio of Amravati, Nanded, Kolhapur, Sangli, Jalgaon, Akola and Malegaon city was 961, 928, 959, 982,

913, 959 and 972 females per thousand male respectively. Sangli city's sex ratio was higher than the other cities and Jalgaon city observed lowest sex ratio than the other cities.

**Similar Size Cities'
Sex Ratio- 2011**

Name of City	Male	Female	Sex Ratio
Amravati	329992	317065	961
Nanded	285433	265006	928
Kolhapur	280366	268870	959
Sangli	253640	249153	982
Jalgaon	240599	219638	913
Akola	217393	208424	959
Malegaon	244080	237148	972

Source: Census 2011.

The sex ratio of Amravati city was decreased than the 2001 census year, and Sangli city's sex ratio was increased but the Jalgaon city's sex ratio was

comparatively stable than the last census year. Nanded and Kolhapur cities' sex ratio was slightly increased in 2011 census.

6. Conclusion:

The similar size cities' sex ratio during the period of 2011 census. The sex ratio of Amravati, Nanded, Kolhapur, Sangli, Jalgaon, Akola and Malegaon city was 961, 928, 959, 982, 913, 959 and 972 females per thousand male respectively. Sangli city's sex ratio was higher than the other cities and Jalgaon city observed lowest sex ratio than the other cities. The sex ratio of Amravati city was decreased than the 2001 census year, and Sangli city's sex ratio was increased but the Jalgaon city's sex ratio was comparatively stable than the last census year. Nanded and Kolhapur cities' sex ratio was slightly increased in 2011 census.

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